

Kyasaur Forest Disease -A re-emerging zoonotic disease

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Abstract

Kyasaur forest disease is a rare tick-borne zoonotic disease that causes acute febrile hemorrhagic illness in humans and monkeys, primarily in Índia's south. The disease is caused by the highly pathogenic KFD virus, which is a member of the Flavivirus genus and the Flaviviridae family. It is a re-emerging vector-borne zoonotic disease (VBZD) in various parts of the world, including Índia.

Introduction

The tick-borne disease Kyasanur Forest disease (KFD), often known as monkey fever, is one of Índia's most serious and long-ignored diseases, producing roughly 400–500 human cases each year in the Western Ghats region of the country's south-western states. The disease causes a flu-like sickness that can lead to hemorrhagic and neurological complications; case fatality rates range from 2% to 10%.

The most prevalent obligate blood-sucking ectoparasites are ticks. Ticks are spreading worldwide and expanding to new geographical places in the modern era, with an increasing number of instances being reported.

Many bacterial, viral, and rickettsial infections are transmitted by ticks, which act as vectors for harmful organisms. Because their bite is harmless, they go overlooked in a considerable majority of cases.

History

In March 1957, the disease was first detected in the Kattinakere village forest, which is located in the Kyasanur forest region in Karnataka, Índia. When officials discovered the infections in the Kattinakere forest, they noticed a sign indicating that they were in the Kyasanur forest range. As a result the name, In the year 1957, the disease first appeared as an

epizootic epidemic among monkeys, killing many of them. As a result, the sickness is also known as "monkey disease" or "monkey fever" in some areas.

In 1989, a patient with fever symptoms was discovered in Nanjani, China, and its viral gene sequence was revealed to be identical to that of the KFD reference virus from 1957 to 2009. This has been questioned, however, because the Indian virus's sequence changes throughout time, and a precise match with the virus sequences from 1957 and 1989 seems unlikely. Using immune response testing, the researchers discovered that birds and humans in the area had been exposed to the virus.

Epidemiology

The disease has a fatality rate of 3-10% and affects 400-500 people each year. The disease was first discovered in Kyasanur village near Sagar in Karnataka's Shivamogga district. The virus has been found in monkeys in Bandipur National Park (Chamarajnar) and the Nilgiris. Human infection occurred in Bandipur as a result of handling infected dead monkeys. In Wayanad, a human carrier was also discovered (Kerala). The disease has been detected in Karnataka's neighboring states, including Kerala, Maharashtra, Goa, Tamil Nadu, and Gujarat.

Zoonosis

Infection in monkeys –

KFD infection causes diarrhea, bradycardia, hypotension, and eventually death in South Indian macaques (*Macaca radiata*).

Man's illness -

- The incubation period lasts between 3 and 8 days.
- KFD is characterized by a sudden onset of fever, cephalalgia, myalgia, anorexia, and insomnia. The patient usually has diarrhoea and vomiting on the third or fourth day
- Severe prostration and papulovesicular lesions on the palate are common occurrences.
- Bradycardia and hypotension are both significant symptoms.
- Coughing and abdominal pain are fewer common symptoms.
- The fever lasts between 6 and 11 days. Following a febrile period of 9 to 21 days, a significant proportion of patients experience a second phase of pyrexia lasting 2 to 12 days, usually accompanied by neurologic symptoms such as stiffness.

Etíology

The KFD vírus is a flavivirus with a diameter of 40-60 nanometers. KFDV's genome is made up of 10,774 nucleotides of single-stranded positive-sense RNA that codes for a single polyprotein that is cleaved post-translationally into three structural (C, prM/M, and E) and seven non-structural (NS1, NS2a, NS2b, NS3, NS4a, NS4b, and NS5) proteins. The genome of KFDV is remarkably similar to that of Alkhurma Hemorrhagic Fever Virus, which is mostly found in Saudi Arabia (>92 percent homologous). These two species, both Flaviviridae members, diverged around 700 years ago and have remained geographically separated ever since.

Transmisiones

Porcupines, rats, squirrels, mice, and shrews are among the animals suspected to be reservoir hosts for the disease. Monkeys are the virus's primary amplifying hosts, and they are also victims. The KFD virus is particularly dangerous to the surili *Presbytis entellus* and the bonnet macaque. They produce a lot of viremia and infect the ticks. The *Haemaphysalis spinigera*, a forest tick, is the disease's vector. Humans become infected after being bitten by tick nymphs. Man is a terminal host, and there is no human-to-human transmission since ticks cannot survive in the human home environment.

Pathogenesis

KFDV pathogenesis is not completely understood. Using mouse models, researchers discovered that KFDV replicated primarily in the brain. Other studies have expanded on this by describing neurological changes in infected organisms. Using KFDV-infected mice, the researchers discovered that KFDV caused gliosis, inflammation, and cell death in the brain. They proposed that KFDV is primarily a neuropathic disease with secondary symptoms caused by this pathogenesis.

Díagnosis

Previously, suspected cases were confirmed in a laboratory by serum inoculation into suckling mice (Swiss Albino mice), and the mice's subsequent death was classified as a KFD Positive case. Hemagglutination inhibition (HI), complement fixation, and neutralisation tests were also used to make a diagnosis. However, new research has introduced more efficient molecular-based diagnostic methods for KFDV. Among these methods are RT-PCR, nested RT-PCR, TaqMan based real-time RT-PCR, Immunoglobulin M antibodies, and ELISA detection of Immunoglobulin G. The two RT-PCR methods work by attaching a primer to the

NS-5 gene, which is highly conserved in the genus to which KFDV belongs. The duration of PCR positivity is 8–10 days after the onset of symptoms. Anti-KFDV antibodies can be detected using ELISA-based methods.

Prevention and Control

- Individual human tick protection, such as protective clothing and the use of repellents, is critical.
- In a field trial in the endemic area, a formalin-inactivated chick embryo fibroblast tissue culture vaccine produced only 59 percent seroconversion. Antibodies to other Flaviviruses, particularly the West Nile virus, appear to interfere with the vaccine's efficacy.
- In mice, a single inoculation of a live vaccine based on an attenuated strain of Langat virus provided 70 to 100 percent protection against large doses of KFD virus for at least 18 months.
- Tick control measures will be implemented in KFD-affected areas.

Tick Control

Follow these guidelines to avoid tick bites and infection-

- Avoid tick-infested areas, especially in the summer.
- Wear light-colored clothing to make ticks visible.
- Wear a long-sleeved shirt, hat, and long pants, with pant legs tucked into socks.
- To avoid overhanging grass and brush, walk in the center of trails.
- When spending a lot of time outdoors in tick-infested areas, check your body for ticks every few hours. Ticks are typically found on the thigh, arms, underarms, and legs. Ticks can be quite small (no bigger than a pinhead).

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